

TOWARDS
A NATIONAL
COLLECTION

Arts and
Humanities
Research Council

COMMISSIONED REPORT

Consolidation Report: Insights from Towards a National Collection Foundation Projects

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Executive Summary

This report was commissioned by the Towards a National Collection Programme Directorate to consolidate the findings of the eight Foundation Projects funded through the programme. The main aims of the report are to digest the research done by each Foundation Project and to examine their scientific contributions to Towards a National Collection, the scholarly community, and the wider cultural heritage sector.

The research was undertaken by Dr Carlotta Paltrinieri between August and December 2022.

This consolidation report is primarily based on the elaboration and cross-analysis of the Foundation Projects' final reports¹ combined with additional readings of relevant reports in the field [See: Resources]. The author has sought further insights from the Foundation Projects' Principal Investigators via 45-minute one-to-one interviews on Microsoft Teams, held between October and December 2022.

To reach its aims, the report offers:

- A cross-comparison of the structure, objectives, and methodology of each Foundation Project, together with a contextualisation within the wider Towards a National Collection ecosystem [Section 1].
- An assessment of the Foundation Projects' contribution to the field, by addressing three areas of impact: their influence on Towards a National Collection's Discovery Projects; their leadership in ongoing scholarly debates and best practice in the digital realm; their legacy and future developments [Section 2].
- A reflection upon the challenges these projects had to face, and how these speak to broader issues within the Higher Education and Cultural Heritage sectors [Section 3].
- A re-elaboration of the Foundation Projects' recommendations for Towards a National Collection, for the sector, and for a future infrastructure: the author will also highlight potential areas of improvement for funding bodies [Section 4].

This study groups the recommendations produced by the Foundation Projects, both in their final reports and in their overall research outputs, under the following categories:

- Actionable Audience Motivations: it is imperative to understand audience motivations and work them into the conception, design, and development phases of research;
- Openness: open data and open source software and outputs are fundamental for ensuring innovative and inclusive research;
- Transparency: Towards a National Collection funded projects need to be transparent to their users throughout all their processes: from decision-making to licensing, to the training of algorithms;
- Representation: a future national collection, and the institutions taking part in it, need to be mindful of what and who it represents.
- Adoption and Enforcement of Standards: the Foundation Projects' findings have clearly demonstrated the importance of developing standards that can be adopted and adapted by organisations with different collections typologies and capacity.

¹ All final reports are available here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/Towards a National Collection/?page=1&size=20>

- Training in Digital Skills: these multi-partner projects have highlighted the importance of training in digital skills for staff, allowing for leadership and growth opportunities during and after the project.

In addition to the recommendations formulated in the Foundation Projects' final reports, other key messages have emerged from the interviews between the author and each Principal Investigator, who were invited to reflect on their projects and achievements, and on the lessons learnt through their participation into Towards a National Collection.

The main findings of this interview phase concern:

- Communication & Community Building: the participation in a multi-project programme has made clear the fundamental role of inter-communication, collaboration, and coordination within each project and across projects: these elements, which took up time and resources in the management of the projects, should be weighted and timed separately.
- Commissioned Research: the external research commissioned by Towards a National Collection Directorate was deemed to be appropriate and relevant, and to respond well to the needs of the sector. However, in the case of two specific pieces of commissioned research - *A Culture of Copyright* commissioned to Dr Andrea Wallace² and *User Research* to Sophia Woodley and Patrick Towell³ - the question of timing was raised: the pivotal findings of these reports would have significantly helped the Principal Investigators of the Foundation Projects in shaping and setting up their projects, as they offer important insights on key issues that should be considered from the start by any cultural heritage research project. In retrospective, this kind of commissions on core components of cultural heritage research could have been even more effective if published, or at least made available, before selecting and awarding the Foundation Projects.
- Digitisation: while digitisation and Digitisation policies are outside the current scope of Towards a National Collection, the work done by the Foundation Projects has highlighted how digitisation is a key factor in developing research involving GLAM collections and needs to be considered in future developments of the programme. In particular, the issues that the funding and governing bodies should address are the unsustainability of partnering up with the private sector to carry out large digitisation campaigns; and the lack of an institutional budget for digitisation in most organisations applying for external research funding, which deprives these organisations of the possibility of participating meaningfully in the advancement and innovation in the field of digital research.
- Directed/Themed Calls: these types of calls from funders can be restrictive for researchers whose important work does not fit into a specific theme or kind of partnerships. The resulting risk is the tendency of shoehorning research projects to fit the funders' calls, instead of meaningfully addressing the need of the sector and tapping into the research potential of cultural heritage institutions with different collections, resources, and expertise.
- Technical Expertise: the participation in a programme that centres on digital research for cultural heritage and humanities has highlighted the difference that competent, specialised technical researchers can make for a project working with digital collections and developing digital methods

² Wallace, Andrea. (2022). *A Culture of Copyright: A scoping study on open access to digital cultural heritage collections in the UK*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6242611>

³ Woodley, Sophia, & Towell, Patrick. (2022). *User Research*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6684165>

and tools. Ensuring the collaboration in cultural heritage projects of such specialised technical researchers, however, is not an easy task: Research Software Engineers and Data Scientists need to be attracted by formulating interesting research questions from a technical point of view, and by offering competitive working conditions.

The report includes: a graph of the network of people and institutions involved in the Foundation Projects [Appendix A]; a list of publications citing the Foundation Projects [Appendix B]; and a list of Resources [Resources].

Abstract

This report was commissioned by the Towards a National Collection Programme Directorate to consolidate the findings of the eight Foundation Projects funded through the programme. The main aims of the report are to digest the research done by each Foundation Project and to examine their scientific contributions to Towards a National Collection, the scholarly community, and the wider cultural heritage sector.

This consolidation report is primarily based on the elaboration and cross-analysis of the Foundation Projects' final reports⁴ combined with additional readings of relevant reports in the field [See: Resources]. The author has sought further insights from the Foundation Projects' Principal Investigators via 45-minute one-to-one interviews on Microsoft Teams, held between October and December 2022.

The report includes: a graph of the network of people and institutions involved in the Foundation Projects [Appendix A]; a list of publications citing the Foundation Projects [Appendix B]; and a list of Resources [Resources].

⁴ All final reports are available here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/Towards a National Collection/?page=1&size=20>

1. Towards a National Collection's Foundation Projects: An Overview

This first section offers a cross-comparison of the structure, objectives, and methodology of each Foundation Project, together with a contextualisation within the wider Towards a National Collection ecosystem.

The Foundation Project grants were awarded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) following a limited competition of proposals from the culture and heritage sector Independent Research Organisations. The awards formed the first stage of the £18.9m UK Research and Innovation Strategic Priority Funded programme, Towards a National Collection, which began in February 2020.

The eight Foundation Projects funded in 2020 were:

- *Heritage Connector* - Principal Investigator: John Stack (Science Museum Group)
- *Provisional Semantics* - Principal Investigator: Emily Pringle (Tate)
- *Practical Applications of IIF⁵* - Principal Investigator: Joseph Padfield (The National Gallery)
- *Heritage PIDs* - Principal Investigator: Rachael Kotarski (The British Library)
- *Locating a National Collection* - Principal Investigator: Gethin Rees (The British Library)
- *Deep Discoveries* - Principal Investigator: Lora Angelova (The National Archives)
- *Engaging Crowds* - Principal Investigator: Pip Willcox (The National Archives)
- *Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects* (Born Digital Objects)- Principal Investigator: Natalie Kane (Victoria & Albert Museum)

The Foundation Projects were devised as short-term, small-scale pilot projects that aimed “to provide evidence and policy recommendations to inform the future development of the ‘national collection’ [...] and to lay the foundations for a virtual national collection by identifying and addressing the current or future challenges facing the formation of such a collection”.⁶ In the initial design of Towards a National Collection, the Foundation Projects also had a major role in feeding into the subsequent Discovery Projects.⁷ Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, this initial timeline changed, impacting the through-line between each phase of the programme [Section 3.1].

⁵ IIF stands for International Image Interoperability Framework.

⁶ Towards a National Collection website, “[Foundation Projects](#)”.

⁷ More about Towards a National Collection Discovery Projects here: https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk/Discovery_Projects

Each Foundation Project was awarded up to £220,000, with a duration between 24 and 36 months:

AHRC reference	Project	Principal Investigator	Original end date	Revised end date	Full Allocated Budget
AH/T011068/1	Heritage Connector	John Stack	Oct 2021	Dec 2021	£201,000
AH/T011076/1	Provisional Semantics	Emily Pringle	31 July 2021	28 Feb 2022	£200,263
AH/T011084/1	Practical applications of IIF	Joseph Padfield	31 Oct 2021	30 April 2022	£220,164
AH/T011092/1	Heritage PIDs	Rachael Kotarski	31 Oct 2021	30 Jan 2022	£197,911
AH/T011114/1	Deep Discoveries	Lora Angelova	April 2021	July 2021	£201,229
AH/T011122/1	Engaging crowds	Pip Willcox	Jan 2022	April 2022	£219,492
AH/T01119X/1	Locating a National Collection	Gethin Rees	31 Jan 2022	31 July 2022	£209,418
AH/T01122X/1	Preserving and sharing born-digital	Natalie Kane	31 July 2021	30 March 2022	£202,135

Data Provided by Dr Javier Pereda, Towards a National Collection's Senior Researcher, and available at: <https://gtr.ukri.org/>

1.1 Structure and Staffing

One of the core principles of the Foundation Projects was the collaboration between Independent Research Organisations and Higher Education Institutions. All projects have been successful at creating meaningful partnerships, despite some institutional and circumstantial challenges [Section 3]. Each one of the six Independent Research Organisations leading the projects⁸ managed to bring together researchers from different backgrounds, career stages, and areas of expertise, providing an exceptional level of interdisciplinary collaboration in an AHRC-funded programme. This demonstrates the potential of digital research in bringing together researchers of different sectors, backgrounds, skillsets, and career levels in the UK and internationally.

⁸ Tate, British Library (2), V&A, National Gallery, The National Archives (2), and the Science Museum Group.

Below, a breakdown of the institutions and organisations involved in all Foundation Projects [see **Appendix A**]:

Project	IROs	HEIs	Private Sector
Heritage Connector	2	1	1
Provisional Semantics	3	1	0
Practical Applications of IIF	6	2	2
Heritage PIDs	6	1	0
Deep Discoveries	2	2	0
Engaging Crowds	3	0	1
Locating a National Collection	3	2	0
Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects	2	1	0

1.2 Aims and Objectives

The aims and objectives underpinning the eight Foundations Projects can be grouped in four main categories:

- A. Linking collections
- B. Revising/Ameliorating current practices
- C. Widening access and participation
- D. Advancing innovation

These four categories align with the overall scope of the Towards a National Collection programme, to “support research that breaks down the barriers that exist between the UK’s outstanding cultural heritage collections, with the aim of opening them up to new research opportunities and encouraging the public to explore them in new ways”.⁹

⁹ *Towards a National Collection* website, “[About Us](#)”.

Each project addresses these four aims, in different ways and to different extents:

1.2.1 Linking Collections

These eight Foundation Projects were selected primarily for their ability of connecting collections from different cultural heritage institutions, of different nature, and of different degrees of digitisation. For instance, *Heritage Connector* delivered a “proof of concept for the application of entity-linking approaches to making connections between online representations of heritage objects”¹⁰, successfully linking the collections from the Science Museum Group, the Victoria & Albert Museum, and Wikidata. The Science Museum Group and the Victoria & Albert Museum collections, together with the National Gallery, the National Portrait Gallery, the British Library, and the Royal Botanic Gardens collections, were also linked through the *Practical Applications of IIF* project, exploring the potential of the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIF) to “virtually connect collections at different organisations”;¹¹ the project has shown that since IIF has developed into a reliable and well-established set of open standards supported by a dedicated international community, utilising IIF services and resources can be an efficient way to share and expand upon high-quality digitised collections. *Heritage PIDs* also based its approach to collection linking on globally-recognised, internationally-adopted standards: Persistent Identifiers; this enabled the project to “draw together the national collection, delivering innovation by adopting a cross-disciplinary and cross-collections approach to the use of an existing technology”.¹² On the other hand, *Deep Discoveries* explored the potential of technological innovation to link collections by developing “a Computer Vision-search software platform for matching content within and across collections, enabling visual records to be linked based on properties such as pattern, style, colour and other visual motifs”.¹³ *Locating a National Collection* was able to outline and explain the advantages of linking collections based on location for both the public audiences and cultural heritage organisations:¹⁴ it linked collections of both historic environment organisations (Historic Environment Scotland, Historic England, English Heritage, National Trust, Historic Royal Palaces) and GLAM collections (British Library and the Portable Antiquities Scheme).

1.2.2 Revising/Ameliorating current practices

Foundation Projects have also focused on the exploration of standards’ adoption and digital research practices across participating organisations, to assess (and provide evidence to) the need of changes across the sector. In particular, *Provisional Semantics* examined various strategies that cultural and heritage organisations can use to incorporate ethical and fair practices in their research projects, as well as in the process of cataloguing and interpreting artifacts. Their research provided “vital insights into the pragmatics of ‘decolonising’ work, and the ways in which this is possible within current organisational hierarchies related to power, knowledge and appetite for change”.¹⁵ *Engaging Crowds* also offered important insights on existing practices across the sector, specifically around participatory methods for digital research: they demonstrated that allowing volunteers to have access to the data they assist in collecting is crucial in citizen

¹⁰ Heritage Connector Final Report, p. 3.

¹¹ Practical Applications of IIF Final Report, p. 5.

¹² Heritage PIDs Final Report, p. 3.

¹³ Deep Discoveries Final Project, p. 3.

¹⁴ Locating a National Collection Final Report, p. 5.

¹⁵ Provisional Semantics Final Report, p. 10.

research, and developed strategies for determining the appropriate licensing conditions for each institution and the most suitable way to share images and data on the internet¹⁶ [Section 1.3.2]. *Born Digital Objects* successfully examined and evaluated the current methods, issues, and difficulties regarding the preservation of born digital cultural heritage in museums and other collecting organizations, and proposed technical pilots that encourage and enable institutions to provide information on born digital objects and associated preservation and conservation documentation, and produced a decision-making model to assist them when acquiring complex born digital objects¹⁷ [Section 1.3.3]. *Heritage PIDs* aimed to “gather evidence on the organisational and cultural barriers that impact on the adoption of PIDs in the sector, and how to overcome these to realise the additional benefits of PID use across collections”; the solutions proposed by the project are improved usage metrics; network analysis of collections; and improved links to enriched or additional information and new perspectives on collections.¹⁸

1.2.3 Widening access and participation

Digital projects have the potential of widening access and participation, both from a users’ and an institutional perspective. The Foundation Projects have amplified the potential of the digital, by making access and participation focal points of their research. *Engaging Crowds* - a project focused specifically on citizen research – demonstrated the importance of studying who is involved in the work, their reasons for participation, and how heritage organisations can improve the experience, which leads to improving the sector’s understanding of how to increase participant satisfaction and involvement.¹⁹ User participation can also be widened by offering a different way to engage with digital collections: *Deep Discoveries* has proven that Computer Vision search can provide means for users with disabilities such as dyslexia, non-native English speakers and those without technical language skills to easily search and discover what they are looking for by removing access barriers. The project also acknowledged that different approaches can be more inclusive for a specific community, but still marginalise others: “Computer Vision search is a technology reliant on visual input. Hence, when speaking of diversifying audiences or ways of engaging, we must consider users who may be visually impaired, and instead rely on Image Descriptions”.²⁰ *Practical Applications of IIF* looked at widening access and participation from an organizational perspective, in addition to a users’ perspective; the project examined the way in which IIF can lower the barriers for participation, especially in the case of smaller institutions, by adopting standards created by larger institutions and maintained through a solid consortium.²¹

1.2.4 Advancing innovation

Heritage Connector explored “the opportunity for computer generated links with Wikidata to provide new levels of structure and machine-readable data that can form the foundation of new types of discovery and access”.²² In order to achieve this, the project developed a bespoke approach for record linkage to Wikidata,

¹⁶ Engaging Crowds Final Report, p. 15.

¹⁷ Preserving and Sharing Born Digital Objects Final Report, p.3.

¹⁸ Heritage PIDs Final Report, p. 3.

¹⁹ Engaging Crowds Final Report, p. 16.

²⁰ Deep Discoveries Final Report, p. 15.

²¹ Practical Applications of IIF Final Report, p. 5.

²² Heritage Connector Final Report, p. 3.

as there were no flexible open-source options available, particularly for low training data and low metadata uses. This approach is fairly new for digitised cultural heritage collections, and therefore represents an important step towards technological innovation.²³ Technological innovation was also at the forefront of *Practical Applications of IIF*, which pinpointed areas requiring additional improvement to fully realize the potential of IIF resources,²⁴ and specifically the application of IIF to 3D representations of collection objects. *Deep Discoveries* also advanced technological approaches to cultural heritage collections by exploring the use of Computer Vision and Explainable Artificial Intelligence techniques to improve the ability of both general audiences and specialist researchers to uncover visual collections in innovative and/or more efficient ways.²⁵ The Foundation Projects have also demonstrated that innovation in the digital sphere does not only stem from, or result in, technological developments, but also from transformational methodologies in research practices: in particular, *Provisional Semantics* had the ability to “pilot methodologies that engage with a ‘decolonisation’ agenda to enable staff to work with colleagues internally and with key stakeholders to describe and interpret collections and catalogues” [Section 3.3].²⁶

1.3 Methodological Approach

All Foundation Projects presented cohesive and thorough desk-based research combined with interviews and surveys, focus groups, and iterations with their respective advisory boards. The strength of their methodology lies in the amalgamation of qualitative research, participatory methods, and technological developments, which demonstrate that the projects’ aims were achieved not only through their research and outputs, but through their everyday activities.

1.3.1 Qualitative Research – Case Studies

Almost all projects have centred their qualitative research on case studies largely based on the collections of the project partners and collaborators: *Provisional Semantics* built case studies around the Imperial War Museum’s [photographic collection](#), the National Trust’s ‘[Clive Museum](#)’ collections, and Tate’s [Panchayat Collection](#). The case studies developed by *Heritage PIDs* assessed the use of Persistent Identifiers at project partners, covering the British Library, National Gallery, Natural History Museum and Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh.²⁷ The Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh ([Herbarium collection](#)) was also one of *Engaging Crowds*’ three citizen research projects built through the Zooniverse platform, together with [HMS NHS: The Nautical Health Service](#) (Royal Museums Greenwich); and The National Archives’ [Scarlets and Blues](#). *Born Digital Objects* selected a series of four objects within the collections of the Victoria & Albert Museum and the British Film Institute as case study subjects to examine the characteristics of born-digital and hybrid objects in collections.²⁸

²³ Knowledge graphs and computer generated links with Wikidata have been particularly researched and applied to libraries and archives’ collections.

²⁴ *Practical Applications of IIF Final Report*, p. 6.

²⁵ *Deep Discoveries Final Report*, p. 1.

²⁶ *Provisional Semantics Final Report*, p. 7.

²⁷ *Heritage PIDs Final Report*, p. 10.

²⁸ *Preserving and Sharing Born Digital Objects Final Report*, p.1.

1.3.2 Participatory Methods

All projects have included some form of community consultation in their methodology, specifically workshops, understanding the importance of listening to different audiences and their different needs; despite the challenges of Covid-19, each project has successfully managed to deliver the workshops online.²⁹ These workshops were not just a tool for information-gathering; they were an integral part of the iterative process during the development and testing of technologies, as well as an important way to establish new collaborations and networks. Some projects have also made extensive use of crowdsourcing, especially *Engaging Crowds*.

The importance of the embedded use of participatory methods in the Foundation Projects should not be underestimated and should be considered as a model for best practice for future projects across the sector [Section 4].

²⁹ For a more detailed description of each projects' workshops, see their Final Reports.

1.3.3 Technological Developments

Almost all projects developed a series of open-source datasets, software and tools, which are now available to the research community and the larger cultural heritage sector:

Foundation Project	Technological Development
Engaging Crowds	Indexing tool ; data sharing platform (via Zooniverse)
Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects	Data model ; Decision Making Model ;
Locating a National Collection	Locolligo ; Peripleo
Practical Applications of IIF	Simple Site ; Simple IIF Discovery ; IIF Collection Explorer ; Tudor Portrait Resource ; The New Digirati Manifest Editor .
Deep Discoveries	Visual Search Prototype
Heritage PIDs	Demonstrator tool (Annotate It!)
Heritage Connector	knowledge graphs and demonstrators: Mapping Locations ; Metadata Explorer ; Visualisation ; Bookmarklet ; SPARQL query interface , proof-of-concept interfaces

Foundation Projects: Areas of Impact

This second section will assess the Foundation Projects' contribution to the field, by addressing three areas of impact: their influence on Towards a National Collection's Discovery Projects; their leadership in ongoing scholarly debates and best practice in the digital realm; their legacy and immediate future developments.

Disclaimers:

- The data used to assess the three areas is true only in the time frame during which this report has last been updated (January 2023). Any future research on the topic should review these statistics.
- The author recognises the limitations of assessing the projects' impact shortly after their end. This report aims at setting the stage for future longer-term assessments.

2.1 Influence on Discovery Projects

Three of the Foundation Projects have directly fed into the 'Discovery Projects', Towards a National Collection's third and larger round of funded projects (£14.5m): the five Discovery Projects selected are "harnessing the potential of new technology to dissolve barriers between collections, with the central aim of empowering and diversifying audiences by involving them in the research and creating new ways for them to access and interact with collections".³⁰ These Discovery Projects share not only objectives and approaches, but involve researchers from the Foundation Projects. The Discovery Project *Transforming Collections* draws upon the knowledge and outcomes of the Foundation Project *Provisional Semantics*, by aiming to uncover suppressed histories, amplify marginalised perspectives, re-evaluate ignored or marginalised artists and artworks, and envision a growing, interconnected "national collection" that incorporates and enhances existing knowledge through diverse, multiple narratives.³¹ *Engaging Crowds* fed into the Discovery Project *Our Heritage, Our Stories*, with the common objective of creating a national collection that is mindful and representative of the widest possible community: *Our Heritage, Our Stories* examines the extensive community-created repository of knowledge about the past, which is often challenging for researchers and the public to access and utilise due to its dispersed state.³² The Discovery Project *The Congruence Engine* team had previously demonstrated in the Foundation Project *Heritage Connector* the feasibility of linking key terms within knowledge graphs through the use of machine learning techniques, including items from Wikidata, as proof of concept. *Heritage Connector* had already used AI to construct a single knowledge graph, on which the *Congruence Engine* is building to "experiment with off-the-peg digital humanities programs and techniques".³³

³⁰ Discovery Projects: https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk/Discovery_Projects

³¹ See the Transforming Collections: Reimagining Art, Nation and Heritage First Report <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7153482>

³² See Our Heritage, Our Stories First Report, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7152511>

³³ The Congruence Engine First Report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7144075>

2.2 Leadership

By leadership the author means the ability to steer debates, practices, and policies in both the academic and the cultural heritage sectors. This ability has been assessed by a) analysing the metrics provided by Zenodo, the opensource repository on which Towards a National Collection has published its grant-funded and commissioned reports; b) tracking citations of the Foundation Projects reports and outputs via Google Scholar and other platforms.

2.2.1 Final Reports Metrics

Below, a table reporting the Zenodo statistics of the eight final reports written by each Foundation Project team (January 2023):

Foundation Project	Unique Views*	Unique Downloads*	Date of publication
Engaging Crowds	269	141	06/10/2022
Born Digital Objects	208	132	04/10/2022
Locating a National Collection	417	182	12/09/2022
Provisional Semantics	839	442	22/07/2022
Practical Applications IIIIF	1,305	655	22/07/2022
Heritage PIDs	647	260	15/03/2022
Heritage Connector	1,631	767	09/02/2022
Deep Discoveries	1,263	281	18/11/2021

* Zenodo definition: Views and Downloads in one hour user-sessions

When examining this data, it is imperative to consider the relationship between the date of publication of the report, its upload on the Zenodo platform, and the metrics of views and unique downloads. It is essential to understand the significance of unique views and downloads, as they do not necessarily indicate a comprehensive reading or use of the report for further research. Nevertheless, these metrics provide a rough indication of the level of interest in the Foundation Projects. Additionally, it should be noted that these figures do not encompass the broader impact of the projects on the community through events and workshops, which play a crucial role in disseminating the outcomes and discoveries.

2.2.2 Citations

The information for this section has been obtained through a cross-search process that involved utilising three major databases, namely Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science. For those who are interested in learning about the complete list of publications that cite the Foundation Projects, they can refer to Appendix B. It's important to note that this cross-search does not encompass citations from the Foundation Projects' own publications, events or the overall programme. If one is interested in getting a more in-depth understanding of these citations, they can find them documented in detail in each Foundation Project final report. The majority of the Foundation Projects' publications are yet to be published. The disparity in the extent of publications that cite the Foundation Projects does not necessarily indicate a greater or lesser degree of interest in the projects themselves. Rather, it serves as a reminder of the importance of promoting online publishing platforms such as Zenodo within the cultural heritage sector. This would aid in disseminating the results and enhancing the impact of funded projects.

2.3 Legacy & Future Developments

This section delves into the future developments of the projects outside of Towards a National Collection and beyond the research outputs listed in the Final Reports: the *Heritage Connector* project will focus on its work with Wikidata and will be at the center of an Early Career Fellowship funded by the Science Museum Group; the *Deep Discoveries* project's User Experience team at Newcastle University may continue working on the prototype separately, but currently there is no internal support from the National Archives to further develop it; *Locating a National Collection's* map interface is being utilised by other projects within the Pelagios network, but there is currently no additional internal support from the British Library; *Practical Applications of IIF's* work at the National Gallery is still being used within the institution and the IIF development is ongoing thanks to collaboration with the IIF Consortium. The *Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects* project continues its research on born-digital objects as it aligns with the Victoria & Albert Museum's mission and interests, with a doctoral student being employed to continue the work on born-digital objects in the museum's collection.

3. Foundation Projects: Challenges

This third section will reflect upon the challenges these projects had to face, and how these speak to broader issues within the Higher Education and Cultural Heritage sectors. For each challenge, the Foundation Projects' teams offered recommendations, which can be found in Section 4.

3.1 Timing

The Foundation Projects started on the same day as the Programme Director (1 February 2020) with minimal notice, all were extended due to the pandemic, meaning they significantly overlapped with the development of Discovery Project proposals and in many cases their start-up. This meant that the Foundation Projects could not feed into the Discovery Projects as meaningfully as originally planned when designing the multi-phase scheme. An issue with timing has also been perceived at the stage of the setting-up of the Foundation Projects: in the implementation of the programme, insufficient time was allotted to establish meaningful partnerships, leading most projects to rely on pre-existing networks of individuals. This situation disproportionately benefited Independent Research Organisations with well-established infrastructures and research capabilities. Additionally, there was an ineffective through-line in the programme, hindering its progression: for some of the researchers involved, the simultaneous development of Discovery Projects bids and working on Foundation Projects proved to be a challenging task. It was also believed that commissioning external research earlier on could have been beneficial as it pertains to fundamental research that could have aided the Foundation Projects in the design of their projects [Section 4.3].

3.2 Institutional Support and Legacy

Another challenge that Foundation Projects' teams had to face, especially after the end of the programme funding, was the inconsistent support from their institutions. The majority of Independent Research Organisations involved in the Foundation Projects did not extend any financial or practical support post-project, including maintaining the partnerships established during externally funded initiatives. This is a result of the lack of institutional support across various sectors, particularly with regards to diversity, equity, and inclusion. The *Provisional Semantics* report emphasizes that "a seeming lack of institutional commitment to change and an aversion to perceived risk can hamper individuals and groups attempting to initiate ethical change. At times, a commitment to and/or difficulty in challenging organisational orthodoxy and the authority of the institutional voice appeared to prevent staff from progressing more ethical, equitable and critical modes of practice than are currently in use".³⁴ There is also a challenge posed by the hierarchical structures of organisations and the pressure to comply with the expectations of the organisation: there seems to be a discrepancy between the level of seniority required to manage and coordinate a grant, and the actual level of expertise and time that can be dedicated to the project.

The primary concern regarding preservation and maintenance of networks and work achieved during the project is what happens post-project. *Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects* pointed out the "issue with the emphasis placed on the role of corporate and business logics in generating the most

³⁴ Provisional Semantics Final Report, p. 39.

challenging barriers to collecting and preserving digital platforms".³⁵ *Provisional Semantics* highlighted that project work, which is time and resource limited, can be perceived as tokenistic and superficial, and thus not a sustainable way of bringing about change. It is imperative to continuously reflect critically, engage in ethical collaboration with stakeholders, and challenge institutional orthodoxies, as well as relinquishing power by institutions and individuals representing them.³⁶ In the case of *Practical Applications of IIF*, supporting a community of practice and providing training and support to those who wish to further engage with the technology, requires funding, support, and advocacy for a successful shared digitised image collection.³⁷

3.3 Ethical Considerations

All Foundation Projects were asked to reflect upon potential ethical issues that might underlie their research: the ethical issues encountered revolved around access, ownership, and equity of research processes and outputs.

The most urgent issue is institutional racism, and the colonial legacy of UK institutions, which permeates the sector and its practices. *Provisional Semantics* raised the concern that efforts to initiate change in large and prominent organisations can be hindered by resistance to change and the persistent difficulty of educating individuals without first-hand experience of personal, institutional, and structural racism and the harm they cause. As a result, the conclusion drawn from the project is that the composition of the research team plays a crucial role in the success of research projects, particularly in terms of whether the team has both the required subject-specific expertise and relevant lived experiences.³⁸

The current way in which funding streams are structured also obstructs an ethical collaboration and cooperation of researchers from different institutions and backgrounds. Directed and themed calls perpetuate the issue of not being able to pay for the participation of crucial stakeholders that are often not covered by the grant because they are not affiliated with a target institution or are not already part of the system. Short-term funding does not allow for an appropriate response to ethical issues: for example, *Deep Discoveries* aimed to explore as part of their project the several problematic or exclusionary aspects of Computer Vision search. However, while their original proposal posed questions regarding the ethical considerations of using visual search in heritage collections, such as "What are the ethical implications of applying visual search to heritage collections?" and "How can we prevent the perpetuation of bias and colonial practices in the virtual world, and how can we attract a more diverse audience to our collections?" it became clear that the magnitude and intricacy of these concerns exceeded the scope of a two-year project.³⁹

The Foundation Projects have also dealt with ethical issues when it comes to ownership of digital reproductions of collection objects, and how these impede an equitable and truly open research: *Engaging Crowds* highlighted that the issue of image rights, which organisations may leverage as a source of income, can pose difficulties. In projects that incorporate machine learning models, it is crucial to consider

³⁵ Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects Final Report, p. 13.

³⁶ Provisional Semantics Final Report, p. 42.

³⁷ Practical Applications of IIF Final Report, p. 34.

³⁸ Provisional Semantics Final Report, p. 39.

³⁹ Deep Discoveries Final Report, p. 7.

intellectual property rights and transparency. Citizen research projects offer a significant contribution to the cultural heritage sector through the efforts of volunteers, which must be recognised and prominently acknowledged on project websites. Additionally, ethical and legal considerations must be taken into account to safeguard any personal data from the volunteers.⁴⁰

3.4 Digital Skills Gap

Most Foundation Projects have highlighted the issue with the wide gap in digital skills of the staff and partners involved, the challenge that this gap poses in building and delivering a digital project. This gap is representative of the sector, and should be addressed with appropriate training.

⁴⁰ Engaging Crowds Final Report, p. 23.

4. Foundation Projects: Recommendations

This fourth and final section deals exclusively with the Foundation Projects' recommendations for the Towards a National Collection programme and the future infrastructure, as well as for the sector,⁴¹ highlighting potential areas of improvement for funding bodies. These recommendations respond to the challenges described in Section 3.

4.1 Recommendations for Towards a National Collection and for a Future Infrastructure

4.1.1. Actionable Audience Motivations

As a Towards a National Collection commissioned report *User Research* has demonstrated,⁴² it is paramount to understand the expectations and motivations of the audiences, including what they need and in what form: the Discovery Projects and the future virtual infrastructure should be based on this understanding. In their final report, *Locating a National Collection* pointed out that the design of the infrastructure for a national collection should take into account the motivations of its intended audience.⁴³ On the same line, *Practical Applications of IIF* recommended that as the Towards a National Collection programme progresses, user studies and evaluations should be conducted to determine the viewer options and functions that future users might need, and which existing IIF compliant image viewers can meet those needs.⁴⁴ *Deep Discoveries* highlighted the importance of striking a balance in online visual collections between giving the user a comprehensive view of the collection and supporting exploration through personalised recommendations, which may limit the user's exposure to diverse items in the collection.⁴⁵ The *Heritage Connector* research is a further demonstration that diverse needs of users should be carefully defined when building and maintaining interfaces for the National Collection, as this process can be time-consuming and costly.⁴⁶

4.1.2 Openness

A Culture of Copyright report demonstrated that open data and open source are crucial for innovative and inclusive research.⁴⁷ Projects should strive for open access data in various formats to meet the needs of different audience demographics, as stated in the *Engaging Crowds* report.⁴⁸ However, barriers exist around

⁴¹ The recommendations explored here are a selection: for a complete list of all projects' recommendations see their Final Reports.

⁴² A report by Sophia Woodley and Patrick Towell, published in 2022: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6684165>

⁴³ *Locating a National Collection* Final Report, p. 2.

⁴⁴ *Practical Applications of IIF* Final Report, p. 31.

⁴⁵ *Deep Discoveries* Final Report, p. 10.

⁴⁶ *Heritage Connector* Final Report, p. 16.

⁴⁷ A report by Andrea Wallace, published in February 2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6242611>

⁴⁸ *Engaging Crowds* Final Report, p. 17.

proprietary collections or those digitised by commercial partners, as noted in the *Provisional Semantics* report. While some organisations want their collections to be discoverable by new audiences and researchers, this may conflict with their commercial goals or revenue streams.⁴⁹ These issues need to be dealt with since project inception and design, and it must be an institutional, if not sectoral, conversation.

4.1.3 Transparency

The work of the Foundation Projects addresses transparency in different areas: in research innovation and technological development, as well as in project management and dissemination. The *Deep Discoveries* report emphasizes the importance of transparency with users on how Computer Vision search models are trained and clarifying that visual similarity may have different meanings to different individuals.⁵⁰ Similarly, *Engaging Crowds* recommends transparency in the decision-making process, development, selection, and training of machine learning models and tools to enable their reuse and ensure openness with volunteers. The report also stresses the importance of making licensing and citation information clear to encourage volunteers to understand how the data can be reused.⁵¹ *Provisional Semantics* suggests that “mechanisms need to be in place to identify when reversion to problematic behaviours are happening and to halt them. Such mechanisms, based on the principle of democratic scrutiny could include building in collective criticality and reflective questioning and obtaining consensus from a fully representative research team on decisions to be taken throughout a project”.⁵²

4.1.4 Representation

The Foundation Projects invite Towards a National Collection and its future developments to reflect on the meaning and implications of the word “national” and to be mindful of the community it aims to represent. In particular, *Locating a National Collection* highlights the benefits of presenting heritage of local significance to broaden the public audience and ensure the collection reflects the entire geography of the UK.⁵³ *Provisional Semantics* stresses the importance of having a team with appropriate subject specialist expertise and lived experience in charge of research projects to shape their design, questions, aims, objectives, methods, and outputs effectively.⁵⁴ *Deep Discoveries* emphasizes the responsibility to critically evaluate which visual collections are made accessible to the public under the label of a “national” collection and assess their representation of the breadth of visual content created by, with, or about our communities.⁵⁵ These issues need to be considered throughout the development of the programme, and must inform and feed into the future virtual collection.

⁴⁹ Deep Discoveries Final Report, p. 15.

⁵⁰ Deep Discoveries Final Report, p. 15.

⁵¹ Engaging Crowds Final Report, p. 17.

⁵² Provisional Semantics Final Report, p. 40.

⁵³ Locating a National Collection Final Report, p. 2.

⁵⁴ Provisional Semantics Final Report, p. 40.

⁵⁵ Deep Discoveries Final Report, p. 15.

4.1.5 Adoption and Enforcement of Standards

As seen in Section 1.2.2, the adoption of standards is highly beneficial to institutions and their digitised and digital collections. It is highly recommended that the National Collection programme formally adopts the use of Persistent Identifiers and IIF for future research projects and activities, and that the National Collection programme and UKRI also support the creation and usage of a UK IIF infrastructure, covering topics such as storage, hosting, management, and sustainability.⁵⁶

4.1.6 Infrastructural Guidelines

Part of the work of the Foundation Projects was to test technologies that could then be further developed by the future virtual collection. Their reports offer recommendations on the best possible interface, and on the integration of textual and visual elements across the virtual collection: *Heritage Connector* suggests creating multiple lightweight interfaces and tools to access the same output dataset using APIs. These APIs should be designed for large-scale ‘bulk’ use;⁵⁷ similarly, *Locating a National Collection* emphasizes the need for a set of interfaces based on user motivations instead of relying on a single interface;⁵⁸ the same idea of creating a set of interfaces was also proposed by the author in the *International Benchmarking Review*.⁵⁹ *Deep Discoveries* recommends an integrated system that combines visual search and semantic filtering based on metadata for effective image retrieval.⁶⁰

4.1.7 Underlying Costs and Technical Training

The Foundation Projects teams identified costs that should be factored in when proposing and managing a project based on digital and digitised collections. As part of their recommendations, *Provisional Semantics* lists that “projects must be fully resourced, including sufficient funding to cover the contributions from internal and external stakeholders from the planning stage onwards”.⁶¹ *Heritage PIDs* has highlighted the costs related to working with bought-in vendors, who might already have appropriate Persistent Identifiers built in, as institutions will still need to train staff in using those technologies at their full potential. For this reason, in their report they recommend future digital projects to “obtain better cost information from organisations earlier in their implementation journey, as well as considering the implementation paths”.⁶² Training in digital skills is seen as central by all Foundation Projects, as it is the most effective solution to bridge the digital divide and to allowing for leadership and growth of staff throughout the project.

⁵⁶ Practical Applications of IIF Final Report, p. 30.

⁵⁷ Heritage Connector Final Report, p. 14.

⁵⁸ Locating a National Collection Final Report, p. 23.

⁵⁹ A report by Carlotta Paltrinieri, published in December 2021: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5793173>

⁶⁰ Deep Discoveries Final Report, p. 14.

⁶¹ Provisional Semantics Final Report, p. 41.

⁶² Heritage PIDs Final Report, p. 18.

4.2 Recommendations for the sector

All recommendations produced by the Foundation Projects in their final reports are extremely beneficial to the programme and its future developments, but perhaps even more so for the larger cultural heritage sector, and any institution dealing with digital and digitised collections. Particularly relevant to the sector are the following recommendations: regarding institutions using participatory methods, *Engaging Crowds'* research has emphasized the importance of maximizing engagement value for the majority of short-term volunteers and effective communication throughout the project. Organisations should prioritise responsiveness and open communication to ensure a successful project outcome. Moreover, volunteers should be recognised and updated on the outcome of their work and data usage.⁶³ On the same line, *Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects* indicate a need for further investigation in areas such as distributed authorship and ownership, legal and intellectual property systems in digital production, and institutional collecting responsibilities for new technologies;⁶⁴ this urge to identifying and widening access is also perceived by *Heritage PIDs*, which pushes for increased access to technical infrastructure, especially for organisations with limited resources.⁶⁵ *Provisional Semantics* research highlights the impact of external factors such as institutional infrastructure, academic disciplines, professional behavior, and socio-political attitudes on cataloguing practice and object description, and insists that it is crucial for researchers and museum workers to understand and critically examine these external factors.⁶⁶

4.3 Further Recommendations

In addition to the official recommendations listed in their reports, other key messages have emerged from the individual conversations between the author and the Principal Investigators, who were invited to reflect on their projects and achievements, and on the lessons learned through their participation in Towards a National Collection. The Principal Investigators' reflections, prompted by the author, addressed the following areas:

4.3.1 Communication & Community Building

The Principal Investigators appreciated Towards a National Collection's effort towards community building, even though all meetings and events were held online due to the circumstances. The participation in a multi-project programme has made clear the fundamental role of inter-communication, integration, and coordination within each project and across projects: these elements, which took up time and resources in the management of the projects, should be weighted and timed separately. In general, there is a perceived need to be more realistic on the actual work required by a project. Some of these issues have been addressed by the extensive work done by the directorate on match-making and expectations for those developing Discovery Projects.

⁶³ Engaging Crowds Final Report, p. 17.

⁶⁴ Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects Final Report, p. 10.

⁶⁵ Heritage PIDs Final Report, p. 17.

⁶⁶ Provisional Semantics Final Report, p. 38.

4.3.2 Commissioned Research

The external research commissioned by the Towards a National Collection directorate was deemed to be appropriate and relevant to the aims and interests of Towards a National Collection and its funded projects, and to respond well to the needs of the sector. However, in the case of two specific pieces of commissioned research - *A Culture of Copyright* commissioned to Dr Andrea Wallace⁶⁷ and *User Research* by Sophia Woodley and Patrick Towell⁶⁸ - the question of timing was raised: the pivotal findings of these reports would have significantly helped the Principal Investigators of the Foundation Projects in shaping and setting up their projects, as they offer important insights on key issues that should be considered from the start by any cultural heritage research project. It was suggested that this kind of commissions on core components of cultural heritage research could have been even more effective if the findings were published, or at least made available, before selecting and awarding the funded projects.

4.3.3 Digitised & Digital Objects

While digitisation and Digitisation policies are outside the scope of Towards a National Collection, the work of the Foundation Projects has highlighted how digitisation is a key factor in developing research involving GLAM collections and needs to be considered in future developments of the programme. In particular, the issues that the funding and governing bodies should address are the unsustainability of partnering up with the private sector to carry out large digitisation campaigns; and the lack of an institutional budget for digitisation in most organisations applying for external research funding, which deprives these organisations of the possibility of participating meaningfully in the advancement and innovation in the field of digital research. Another issue is the ambiguity of attitude and practices around digital collection objects, meaning objects that were created originally in a digital form: a future virtual collection needs to factor in and respond to the different nature of these objects, and understand that they are increasingly becoming a crucial component of cultural heritage collections that should not be overlooked.

4.3.4 Directed/Themed Calls

These types of calls from funders can be restrictive for researchers whose important work does not fit into a specific theme or kind of partnerships. The risk is the tendency of shoehorning research projects to fit the funders' calls, instead of meaningfully addressing the need of the sector and tapping into the research potential of cultural heritage institutions with different collections and staff expertise. Most of the current calls for digital projects seem to push for developing tools that are sometimes not linked to actual needs; there needs to be more reflection around these tools and the practices behind them, and tools development should be an integral part of research and curatorial practices.

⁶⁷ Wallace, Andrea. (2022). *A Culture of Copyright: A scoping study on open access to digital cultural heritage collections in the UK*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6242611>

⁶⁸ Woodley, Sophia, & Towell, Patrick. (2022). *User Research*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6684165>

4.3.5 Technical Expertise

The participation in a programme that centres on digital research has highlighted the issue with the wide gap in digital skills of the staff and partners involved in the Foundation Projects, and the difference that competent, specialised technical researchers can make for a project working with digital collections and developing digital methods and tools. Ensuring the collaboration in cultural heritage projects of such specialised technical researchers, however, is not an easy task: Research Software Engineers and Data Scientists need to be attracted by formulating challenging and rewarding research questions from a technical point of view, and by offering competitive working conditions.

Appendix A

Visualisation of people and organisations involved in each project

Appendix B

Foundation Projects Collectively:

O'Sullivan James. (2022). Bloomsbury Handbook to the Digital Humanities. London UK: Bloomsbury Academic.

National Diet Library Japan (2021), The British Library (BL) announces the release of an interim report on a national project, "Towards a National Collection," in which the library is involved.

<https://current.ndl.go.jp/car/43361>

Individual Projects:

Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects

The Creative Research And Innovation Centre: Collecting and Archiving Immersive Experiences

<https://craic.lboro.ac.uk/essays/collecting-and-archiving-immersive-experiences/>

Medium: Minecraft Cambridge

<https://digitalpreservation-blog.lib.cam.ac.uk/minecraft-cambrige-part-1-3b07012645cb>

Locating a National Collection

Pelagios – Connecting Histories of Place. Part II: From Community to Association

Rebecca Kahn, Leif Isaksen, Elton Barker, Rainer Simon, Pau de Soto, and Valeria Vitale

International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing 2021 15:1-2, 85-100

<https://www.eupublishing.com/doi/epub/10.3366/ijhac.2021.0263>

Provisional Semantics

Digital Benini: Use of derogatory, racist and harmful language

<https://digitalbenin.org/documentation/use-of-derogatory-racist-and-harmful-language>

Humbel, Marco; (2022) "Participatory Action Research for a Digital Humanities research project: Investigating Open GLAM in the context of Social Movement Archives". In: Proceedings of the Digital Humanities 2022. (pp. 249-252)

https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10152991/1/Humbel_Participatory_Action_Research_for_a_DH_Project_OpenGLAM.pdf

Baker, James; Salway, Andrew; Roman, Cynthia (2022) "Detecting and Characterising Transmission from Legacy Collection Catalogues", Digital Humanities Quarterly.

<http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/16/2/000615/000615.html#pringle2020>

Hazan, Susan (2020), "Mining Big Data for Agile Narratives", in Proceedings of the Museum Big Data Conference 2020.

https://www.musesphere.com/2020/images/Mining_Big_Data_for_Agile_Narratives_Hazan.pdf

Cox, Oliver, "From Power to Enslavement: Recent Perspectives on the Politics of Art Patronage and Display in the Country House", in Art and the Country House

<https://doi.org/10.17658/ACH/TE581>

Lucy Bayley, "Seep Between the Mortar: Sociotechnical Imaginaries in Digital Media at Tate" Stedelijk Studies Journal 10 (2020). DOI: [10.54533/StedStud.vol10.art04](https://doi.org/10.54533/StedStud.vol10.art04)

Vawda, Hassan (2022) "مِزْجِيس wineglass: the National Trust's Powis Castle and the Clive of India Collection" in Roots and Routes: Research on Visual Cultures

<https://www.roots-routes.org/%D8%AC%D8%A7-%D9%85%D9%90is-wineglass-the-national-trusts-powis-castle-and-the-clive-of-india-collection-by-hassan-vawda/>

Ortolja-Baird Alexandra, Nyhan Julianne, "Encoding the haunting of an object catalogue: on the potential of digital technologies to perpetuate or subvert the silence and bias of the early-modern archive", Digital Scholarship in the Humanities, Volume 37, Issue 3, September 2022, Pages 844–867,

<https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqab065>

Dalal-Clayton Anjalie, Puri Purini Ilaria (2021), Doing the work: Embedding anti-racism and decolonisation into museum practice

https://contemporaryartsociety.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/FullBook_a_compressed-compressed.pdf#page=44

Practical Applications of IIIF

Stevenson Jane, The Archives Hub and IIIF: supporting the true potential of images on the Web

<https://blog.archiveshub.jisc.ac.uk/2021/10/26/the-archives-hub-and-iiif-supporting-the-true-potential-of-images-on-the-web/>

Stifter, David and Cnockaert-Guillou, Nina and Färber, Beatrix and Hayden, Deborah and Ní Mhaonaigh, Máire and Tucker, Joanna and Yocum, Christopher Guy (2022) Developing a Digital Framework for the Medieval Gaelic World: Project Report. Developing a Digital Framework for the Medieval Gaelic World: Project Report.

<https://www.qub.ac.uk/schools/ael/Research/ResearchinLanguages/Fileupload/Filetoupload,1334209,en.pdf>

Persistent Identifiers:

Cope, Jez (2020), When is a persistent identifier not persistent? Or an identifier?

<https://blogs.bl.uk/digital-scholarship/2020/09/when-is-a-persistent-identifier-not-persistent-or-an-identifier.html>

Sotirova, Kalina. (2020). FAIR Principles for Digital Repositories: Essence and Applications for Heritage Objects. Cultural and Historical Heritage: Preservation, Presentation, Digitalization. 6. 64-76.

<https://web.archive.org/web/20220124130358id/http://www.math.bas.bg/vt/kin/files/papers/62/06-KIN-6-2-2020.pdf>

Heritage Connector:

Sotirova, Kalina. (2020). FAIR Principles for Digital Repositories: Essence and Applications for Heritage Objects. Cultural and Historical Heritage: Preservation, Presentation, Digitalization. 6. 64-76.

<https://web.archive.org/web/20220124130358id/http://www.math.bas.bg/vt/kin/files/papers/62/06-KIN-6-2-2020.pdf>

Juhee Park (2022) 'We want to know more than that': lessons learnt from the public workshop on collections data at the V&A, Museum Management and Curatorship, DOI: [10.1080/09647775.2022.2111331](https://doi.org/10.1080/09647775.2022.2111331)

Boer, Viktor de et al. "The Benefits of Linking Metadata for Internal and External Users of an Audiovisual Archive." International Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research (2018).

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Benefits-of-Linking-Metadata-for-Internal-and-Boer-Bruyn/fdcad86d7ab6bb453ff29963148f097a3a32f166>

Maria Leonor Guimarães Dias Amaral Teixeira (2020) Os Impactos da Cultura Digital na Comunicação em Museus. Um olhar sobre a Comunicação Digital dos Museus Nacionais em Portugal

<https://repositorio-aberto.up.pt/bitstream/10216/130636/2/432556.pdf>

Golub, K., & Liu, Y.-H. (Eds.). (2021). Information and Knowledge Organisation in Digital Humanities: Global Perspectives (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003131816>

Deep Discoveries

Юмашева, Юлия Юрьевна. "Историческая наука, архивы, библиотеки, музеи и искусственный интеллект: что день грядущий нам готовит?." Документ. Архив. История. Современность. Вып. 21 21 (2021): 247-279.

https://elar.urfu.ru/bitstream/10995/104227/1/dais_2021_21_021.pdf

Resources

Foundation Projects Final Reports

Winters, Jane, Stack, John, Dutia, Kalyan, Unwin, Jamie, Lewis, Rhiannon, Palmer, Richard, & Wolff, Angela. (2022). *Heritage Connector: A Towards a National Collection Foundation Project Final Report*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6022678>

Pringle, Emily, Mavin, Helen, Greenhalgh, Tate, Dalal-Clayton, Anjalie, Rutherford, Ananda, Bramwell, Jane, Blackford, Katie, & Balukiewicz, Kim. (2022). *Provisional Semantics: Addressing the challenges of representing multiple perspectives within an evolving digitised national collection (Version 2)*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7081347>

Padfield, Joseph, Bolland, Charlotte, Fitzgerald, Neil, McLaughlin, Anne, Robson, Glen, & Terras, Melissa. (2022). *Practical applications of IIF as a building block towards a digital National Collection*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884885>

Kotarski, Rachael, Kirby, Jack, Madden, Frances, Mitchell, Lorna, Padfield, Joseph, Page, Roderic, Palmer, Richard, & Woodburn, Matt. (2022). *Persistent Identifiers as IRO Infrastructure: A Towards a National Collection Foundation Project Final Report*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6359926>

Angelova, Lora, Ogden, Bernard, Craig, Jack, Chandrapal, Hari, & Manandhar, Dipu. (2021). *Deep Discoveries: A Towards a National Collection Foundation Project Final Report*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5710412>

Seaward, Louise, Willcox, Pip, Blickhan, Samantha, Bligh, Stuart, Butler, Will, Fulton, Liz, Haston, Elspeth, Hawkins, Ashleigh, Hutcheon, Rebecca, King, Sally, Kocsis, Andrea, Lintott, Chris, Miller, Grant, Nash, Trevor, O'Donnell, Jim, Ogden, Bernard, Salmon, Martin, & Smith, Thomasina. (2022). *Engaging Crowds: citizen research and cultural heritage data at scale*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7152031>

Rees, Gethin, Gadd, Stephen, Horgan, John, Hunt, Alex, Isaksen, Leif, Morris, Victoria, Musson, Anthony, Simon, Rainer, Strachan, Peter, & Vitale, Valeria. (2022). *Locating a National Collection (LaNC)*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7071654>

Kane, Natalie, Arrigoni, Gabriella, McKim, Joel, McConnachie, Stephen, & Palmer, Richard. (2022). *Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects Across the National Collection*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7144616>

Other Reports

Andrea Wallace. (2022). *A Culture of Copyright: A scoping study on open access to digital cultural heritage collections in the UK*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6242611>

Paltrinieri, Carlotta. (2021). *International Benchmarking Review: A Towards a National Collection Report*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5793173>

Lorna Hughes, Marc Alexander, Hannah Barker, Riza Batista-Navarro, Ewan D Hannaford, Goran Nenandic, & Pip Willcox. (2022). *Our Heritage, Our Stories: Linking and searching community-generated digital content to develop the people's national collection*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7152511>

Rebecca Taylor, Johanna Walker, Simon Hettrick, Philippa Broadbent, David de Roure. (2022). *Shaping data and software policy in the arts and humanities research community*. <https://www.ukri.org/publications/shaping-data-and-software-policy-in-the-arts-and-humanities-research-community/>

Sophia Woodley, Patrick Towell. (2022). *User Research*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6684165>

susan pui san lok, Anjalie Dalal-Clayton, Christopher Griffin, Hannah Barton, Mick Grierson, Athanasios Velios, Ananda Rutherford, Charlotte Webb, Kit Bower-Morris, Jerneja Rebernak, & Fleur Kaminska. (2022). *Transforming Collections: Reimagining Art, Nation and Heritage*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7153482>